

IMPROVING JOINT-STOCK COMPANY OPERATIONS THROUGH INTRODUCING CORPORATE GOVERNANCE EDUCATION IN THE ERA OF DIGITALISATION

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Teaching corporate governance concepts applicable to Joint-Stock Companies (JSCs) in developing economies is becoming increasingly important in the current era of digitalisation and a competitive business environment. In this context, introducing new modules on the main corporate governance mechanisms (such as boards of directors, effective internal control systems, regular financial reporting and auditing, and others) that are required for closely monitoring the performance of executive directors (i.e. managers) of the JSCs is a key element of the current competitive market economy. Equipping students with contemporary corporate governance mechanisms and familiarising them with the key concepts of this subject enables them to apply these mechanisms effectively in the JSCs when they start their jobs. When the JSCs operating in Uzbekistan, including the Stock Exchanges and other financial institutions, have appropriate corporate governance boards and organise their performance in line with generally adopted corporate governance frameworks, these companies will be able to successfully compete in the current global market environment.

At the same time, it is important to inform individual investors, family owners, institutional shareholders, and other types of shareholders about the role of corporate governance systems in monitoring managerial activities in these JSCs. Teaching corporate governance frameworks to students will also provide useful information and knowledge about the accountability of the JSCs to these investors, because students will work with them and regularly contact them. When these investors have clear information about the stock ownership structure of these JSCs, their boards of directors (executive and non-executive directors), accounting/auditing functions, and other operational factors, they can quickly make their investment decisions and make long-term investments in these companies. Subsequently, JSCs will be able to gather the required financial capital to expand their operations. Therefore, introducing and further enhancing corporate governance education during the digitalisation era plays an important role in familiarising students (and subsequently other individuals/institutions with capital that could be invested in the local stock markets) and enabling local companies to gain the required capital for their successful operations.

When capital stock markets facilitate efficient and effective trading of the securities (stocks or shares) of the JSC, individual investors and other capital providers (such as institutional investors, foreign investors, and others) may actively participate in these trades by acquiring and selling the available stocks in the market. In the current digitalisation period, one important benefit of this stock market is that individual investors (along with large investors) will be able to participate in this stock market and make small investments. These investments are very important and beneficial for developing economies, because the small investments of individuals will help JSCs accumulate large funds (by selling their stocks in the market) and make the necessary long-term investments to expand their operations further.

A country's corporate governance system comprises all necessary rules, regulations, practices, and principles on the basis of which organisations are directed, managed and controlled. To timely account to shareholders and to provide the required information, the JSCs should have effective corporate governance systems, which may include several laws and other regulations. For example, the UK Corporate Governance Code defines corporate governance as "the system by which companies are directed and controlled" (Cadbury, 1992), while the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2023) defines it as "a set of relationships between a company's board, its shareholders and other stakeholders".

Several important regulations have been adopted in Uzbekistan to improve its corporate governance framework as part of its broader economic reforms. These include laws on joint-stock companies, securities markets, and corporate governance principles. For example, in Uzbekistan, there have been a wide range of

updates by introducing new legal frameworks to align with international standards, such as the “Law on Joint-Stock Companies” in 2019 and “Law on Limited Liability Companies” in 2020.

Boards of directors In JSCs, there is a separation of stock ownership and control, with shareholders buying shares and providing capital, while the directors’ responsibility is to manage this capital and generate investment returns for shareholders. This separation between corporate ownership and management creates agency problems (i.e., conflicts of interest between shareholders and managers). The board of directors is one of the main mechanisms of corporate governance, as it directs, leads and controls the company, as well as monitors management on behalf of shareholders, and links managers with shareholders. The primary roles of boards are to ensure that management acts in the best interests of shareholders and that other stakeholders’ interests are protected. Corporate strategy formulation and policy making are also primary duties of directors: they generate and review alternative long-term strategies that lead towards the achievement of the firm’s purpose. They are also responsible for confirming long-term strategies/planning and monitoring managerial activities. Similar to the corporate governance systems in other developing economies (with concentrated share ownership by family investors and state agencies), the main objective of the corporate governance system in Uzbekistan is to mitigate such agency problems between managers and shareholders in JSCs and in State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs). The national corporate governance codes applicable to Uzbekistan’s JSCs should set out the roles and responsibilities of the board members (including the executive directors and independent non-executive directors), the accountants and auditors. The codes should also specify the composition, structure, independence and effectiveness of the board and its committees (such as the audit committee, risk committee, remuneration committee and sustainability committee). These committees should be responsible for financial reporting, internal control, auditing and other aspects of corporate activities. All executive directors and other members of the board (such as the Chairman of the board and non-executive directors) should be closely familiar with the corporate governance regulations, including the above-mentioned laws and other regulations. Therefore, it is very important to introduce corporate governance subjects in the Higher Education of Uzbekistan. These module equip student with the required knowledge on the operations of the JSCs in the free-market business environment and the role of boards of directors in these companies. Additionally, these new teaching modules and courses should focus on improving the skills and knowledge of Chief Executive Officers, other executive directors and non-executive directors through training programmes and capacity-building initiatives. These efforts aim to inspire a deeper understanding of corporate governance principles and practices among business leaders. All investors (individuals, families, state organisations and other institutional investors) should receive regular information about the financial performance of the JSCs and their expected dividend returns. Therefore, the recording of business transactions and financial reports on the company’s financial performance and financial position play important role in corporate governance. Accounting information and financial reporting It is also important that the management teams of these JSCs account for all accounting transactions and prepare their financial statements in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). Uzbekistan has mandated the adoption of IFRS for publicly listed companies, which has improved the transparency and comparability of financial statements. This is a critical element in enhancing investor confidence and ensuring that companies are held accountable. Investors make their investment decisions based on accounting information. In this process, the investors use information about the performance and financial position of the company to make their investment decisions, which may involve: (1) buying, selling or holding equity and debt instruments; (2) providing or settling loans and other forms of credit; (3) exercising rights to vote on management actions (Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting, 2018). With fully disclosed and transparent accounting information, shareholders will be in a better position to monitor company management. Therefore, accounting is an essential aspect of a well-functioning corporate governance system.

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As reliable and faithfully represented accounting information is required by all stakeholders in making their investment decisions, it is necessary to make institutional restructuring in the relevant organisations. Accounting information also play role in balancing the interests of other stakeholders. When high-quality accounting information is transparently and timely disclosed, large and minority shareholders will be able to make appropriate investment decisions that generate share price gains and dividends. In such cases, local, national, and foreign investors will be more interested in investing their available capital. Employees with share ownership, remuneration packages, pension fund contributions and other stakes in the business will also be more actively involved in stock market investments.

Teaching advanced-level accounting standards, such as IFRS, in undergraduate/postgraduate programmes is another important factor in establishing a good corporate governance system, because annual financial reports based on these international standards provide reliable information required for the investors' decision-making. Accounting data on companies' internal activities, provided to shareholders and other stakeholders, provides useful information for corporate investment decisions. Additionally, alongside introducing new corporate governance modules, there should be fundamental advances in teaching both Financial Accounting and Management Accounting modules. Financial Accounting helps investors by offering valuable insights into a company's financial performance and position, whereas Management Accounting provides internal management with detailed inputs and information about the state of affairs in the company. Thus, accountants play a paramount role in helping organisations establish effective and controlled corporate governance systems, which are reported using both Financial and Management Accounting.

Enhancement of the capital (stock) markets

An active and transparent capital market can help enforce good corporate governance practices, as companies seeking to raise capital are required to adhere to stricter governance standards. Uzbekistan has been working to develop its capital markets, which are closely linked to corporate governance improvements.

Providing equal access to accounting information and balancing the interests of all shareholders (including large and minority shareholders, institutional investors, employees and other stakeholders) will contribute to the development of the stock market. With timely accounting information, such stakeholders further develop stock markets and enable companies to raise the required capital for their investments.

Capital (securities) market reforms will positively impact the further development of the capital market (i.e., the stock exchange and other related financial markets) in Uzbekistan. Teaching corporate governance modules in the Higher Education institutions of Uzbekistan will also contribute to the development of capital markets, including active stock markets, where JSCs will be able accumulate the funds required for their long-term capital investments.

Corporate governance and sustainability issues

Additionally, corporate governance tools and mechanisms should also focus on corporate sustainability issues. The Brundtland Committee of the United Nations stated in 1987 that corporate sustainability is about "Ensuring the needs of today's world are met while at the same time ensuring that the ability for future generations to meet their own needs is not compromised." In other words, companies need to meet the current requirements of all stakeholders (including shareholders, employees, customers, suppliers, community and other stakeholders). Importantly, they need to meet the needs of the current stakeholders (as stated above) without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

Therefore, the current corporate governance topic should also take into consideration the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) of the JSCs in Uzbekistan. It should discuss how the management team should develop and implement strategies to achieve the company's CSR objectives. In other words, the newly developed corporate governance frameworks should monitor every management function, from business planning and internal controls to corporate disclosure and mandatory/voluntary CSR obligations.

Conclusion

In sum, investors need to receive regular financial reports and information about their investment returns. In the current digitalised era, it is not difficult to make all financial information publicly available. Corporate governance mechanisms, such as boards of directors, internal control systems, preparation of financial statements based on the generally accepted accounting standards and auditing the financial statements.

To development effective corporate governance system in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take into consideration several important phases that need to be implemented step-by-step:

Strengthening the protection of shareholders (large and minority shareholders) and enhancing the stock market in financing the registered companies;

Providing timely accounting disclosures about the firm's performance and expected dividends;

Introducing new employee reward schemes in order to improve their involvement in stock market investments;

Issuing Employee Share Ownership Plans (ESOP) and other stock ownership rewards;

Introducing performance-related pay packages, bonuses and long-term incentive plans;

Allocation of partial wages/remunerations to long-term oriented pension funds (in addition to State pension funds), which will, in turn, make investments into productivity-enhancing capital;

Establishing a well-functioning stock market and attracting the required finances;

Attracting long-term oriented investors and encouraging minority investors to invest in the stock market;

Encouraging employees to work harder to own equity stakes, pension and other work-related reward schemes that might lead them to make innovations;

Boosting the local communities' investment in stock markets by closely monitoring share price gains and dividends.

Therefore, it is also important to teach students about the operations of the stock markets and how companies should issue the stocks (shares) in these markets. An effective corporate governance system at the national levels play important role in organising the activities of the stock markets and JSCs. At the and also following the international

One of the distinguishing characteristics of these study programmes is that they are based on research-led teaching. Thus, to develop such undergraduate and postgraduate degree programmes, we should consider the possibility of study programmes based on research-led teaching, taking into consideration the current economic and business requirements in Uzbekistan.

These strengths reflect Uzbekistan's ongoing efforts to create a more transparent, accountable, and investor-friendly corporate environment, which is crucial for the country's economic development and integration into the global economy. Furthermore, in the current digitalised era, it is relatively cost-effective to provide all useful information (confirmed by the boards of directors) to the investors. Therefore, all investors (including individual investors who are currently not actively involved in the capital market trading) will be interested to make their investors to the securities issued by the JSCs in Uzbekistan. This will enable the companies to have their required capitals o expend their operations in highly profitable business areas, which will positively contribute to further development of Uzbekistan.

References